

Supplementary Table S4. Primer list.

	Primer Name	Primer Sequence (5' -> 3')	Description	Reference
Mutant Construction Primers				
aceE VC2414	aceE Upstream Homology F	GTGGAATTCCTCCGGGAGAGCTCAATATTTTGTCTTTAATCAACTCTTG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceE Upstream Homology R	CATTACTTTCTACCTTCAAGCGATCTACTCTCTGTGG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceE Downstream Homology F	CCAACGAGAAGGATAGATGCCTTGAAGGTAGGAAAAGTAATG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceE Downstream Homology R	CCGCGGACATGTACAGAGCTGACGACTGGGAAGCATG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceE pKAS32 Seq Primer F1	GAACTGGAGAGCATGATGTGGAAG	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceE pKAS32 Seq Primer F2	CAGAAATTTAACTCTTACATCGC	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceE pKAS32 Seq Primer R1	CAAAAGTGCAGTACTCCAT	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceE pKAS32 Seq Primer R2	CTGCACCTTCCGCTCAA	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceE Deletion Detection F	CACCTCTAGCCATCAAGTCC	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study
	aceE Deletion Detection R	GTAGTCTGACTCTTCTTCAGG	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study
aceF VC2413	aceF Upstream Homology F	GTGGAATTCCTCCGGGAGAGCTTCTACTACAAGAAGCGACTTC	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceF Upstream Homology R	TTTCGCCACCCGAGAATGCGCTTAAGCGTACAGCGGTTGGT	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceF Downstream Homology F	ACCAACCCGCTGTACGCTTAAGCGCATCTCGGGTGGCGAAA	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceF Downstream Homology R	CCGCGGACATGTACAGAGCTTTCGCTTCAACGCGCGTC	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	aceF pKAS32 Seq Primer F1	GTACAACGCTGACCGGTAA	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceF pKAS32 Seq Primer F2	ATCGCAGCGACTGACTACAT	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceF pKAS32 Seq Primer R1	CAGCGCATCGGTTGAATC	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceF pKAS32 Seq Primer R2	GCTCATTTGCACTCTGTAGTC	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	aceF Deletion Detection F	TCCGTCAAATCGGTATCTACA	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study
	aceF Deletion Detection R	CGCATCTGAACGCTCAGCT	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study
pfIA VC1869	pfIA Upstream Homology F	GTGGAATTCCTCCGGGAGAGCTTCACTGACTCGAAAAAAG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	pfIA Upstream Homology R	AGAGGATGAAGAGCGCTTCTCAGTTATG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	pfIA Downstream Homology F	AGAAGCGCTTCTATCTCTCGACGTTATC	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	pfIA Downstream Homology R	TGCGCATGCTAGCTATAGTTAACTCGGGTTCAGTTAC	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	pfIA pKAS32 Seq Primer F	AATCTCAGACACCTTGTGGAC	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	pfIA pKAS32 Seq Primer R	GCCAGATATAAAGGGAGTTAAGC	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	pfIA Deletion Detection F	GCTGTGCTTCACTACTGAG	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study
pfIA Deletion Detection R	GGATTCTGCATCGCATGATAC	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study	
lacZ VC2338	lacZ Upstream Homology F	GTGGAATTCCTCCGGGAGAGCTGCCACCAAACTAAGCTTC	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	lacZ Upstream Homology R	GCTCTCTGGCCCTCAAGCCGAGGAGTAAAG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	lacZ Downstream Homology F	GGCTTAGGGGCCAGAGGCTTAAGGC	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	lacZ Downstream Homology R	TGCGCATGCTAGCTATAGTTAGCAGTGAAGCCGGTG	pKAS32 construction primer	This study
	lacZ pKAS32 Seq Primer F	GATAACCAATCGCAAAACCAACT	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	lacZ pKAS32 Seq Primer R	TCTCATCCGTCAGGACATAGAAAC	pKAS32 sequencing primer	This study
	lacZ Deletion Detection F	GAAATTGATCGGTCGATAGGCTG	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study
lacZ Deletion Detection R	CCGAGTCCATAACTCTTCTCTCTTA	Isogenic deletion verification primer	This study	
pKAS32	pKAS32 Multiple Cloning Site Seq Primer F	GCCTCTAAGGTTTTAAGTTT	pKAS32 specific sequencing primer	Lab Collection
	pKAS32 Multiple Cloning Site Seq Primer R	CTTCAAGGTAGCGGTTACC	pKAS32 specific sequencing primer	Lab Collection
toxT VC0838	1531	CAACTTCTGTAGTTAATGCAATCCC	toxT deletion verification primer	Waters Lab Collection
	1532	CCCTCCAGTAAATTTTCAATAATGTGC	toxT deletion verification primer	Waters Lab Collection
Complementation Primer Sets				
aceE VC2414	pMMB66EH aceE ORF F	CAGGAAACAGAAATTCCTCCGGGATGTCTGACATGAAGCATGAC	pMMB66EH aceE ORF construct primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceE ORF R	CTCATCCGCCAAAACAGCCATTAAGCGTACAGCGGGTGG	pMMB66EH aceE ORF construct primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceE ORF Seq Primer 1	CTGCGTGCATCGAAGAAAGA	pMMB66EH aceE ORF sequencing primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceE ORF Seq Primer 2	CTGTTATGGTAAACGGTAAAG	pMMB66EH aceE ORF sequencing primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceE ORF Seq Primer 3	GTACCTGAAACTGGAAGAAAG	pMMB66EH aceE ORF sequencing primer	This study
aceF VC2413	pMMB66EH aceF ORF F	CAGGAAACAGAAATTCCTCCGGGTTGAAGGTAGGAAAAGTAATG	pMMB66EH aceF ORF construct primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceF ORF R	CTCATCCGCCAAAACAGCCATTAACAGTACAGACAGCAGC	pMMB66EH aceF ORF construct primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceF ORF Seq Primer 1	AGCAGCGGCAGCACCAGC	pMMB66EH aceF ORF sequencing primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceF ORF Seq Primer 2	AGATCAAAGTGGCTACAGGCGA	pMMB66EH aceF ORF sequencing primer	This study
	pMMB66EH aceF ORF Seq Primer 3	GAGCAAAAACGCGATGGAAAGC	pMMB66EH aceF ORF sequencing primer	This study
pfIA VC1869	pMMB66EH pfIA ORF F	CAGGAAACAGAAATTCCTCCGGGATGTCTTACCATTGGTCAATTC	pMMB66EH pfIA ORF construct primer	This study
	pMMB66EH pfIA ORF R	CTCATCCGCCAAAACAGCCATCAATTTTACGTTTGAAGTATAC	pMMB66EH pfIA ORF construct primer	This study
pMMB66EH	pMMB66EH Multiple Cloning Site Seq Primer F	TGCATAATTCGTGTCTGCTCA	pMMB66EH specific sequencing primer	This study
	pMMB66EH Multiple Cloning Site Seq Primer R	CTACGGCGTTTCACTCTGTA	pMMB66EH specific sequencing primer	This study
RT-qPCR Primer Sets				
toxT VC0838	toxT qPCR F	ACTGATGATCTTGTGCTATGGAG	qPCR Primer	This study
	toxT qPCR R	CATCCGATTCGTTCTTAATTCACC	qPCR Primer	This study
ctxA VC1475	ctxA qPCR F	TGGAATCCCACCTAAAGCAG	qPCR Primer	This study
	ctxA qPCR R	TTGTTAGGCACGATGATGGA	qPCR Primer	This study
recA VC0543	recA qPCR F	GGGTAACCTCAAGCAATCCA	qPCR Primer	This study
	recA qPCR R	CCACTCTCGCTTCTTTG	qPCR Primer	This study
tcpA VC0828	tcpA qPCR F	ACGCAAAATGCTGCTACACAG	qPCR Primer	This study
	tcpA qPCR R	CCCCTACGTTGTAACCAA	qPCR Primer	This study